

CSI-COP

Citizen Scientists Investigating Cookies and App GDPR compliance

Deliverable D1.10 | D9

CSI-COP Data Management Plan 3

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	x
R	Report, DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs, DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc., OTHER: Other (Database, online tools, questionnaires, etc)	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CS	Citizen science
DMP	Data management plan
DPIA	Data protection impact assessment
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
GDPR	The EU's General data protection regulation that came into force in May 2018
Meta-data	Anything that describes a data file, for example, the file type, file size, what is in the file (such as website or app name). If a report, who authored a report with the data.

Key Terms

Cookies; data management; data protection; F.A.I.R; GDPR; personal data; privacy, purpose limitation, and transparency.

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Executive Summary

This is the third and final CSI-COP data management plan (DMP3) detailing the data produced and data collected during the final period in the project, and since the submission of the second data management plan (DMP2; D1.9|D8) to the EU in June 2022. DMP3 presents the data created and gathered during the citizen science participation phase actively investigating compliance of the GDPR with respect to transparency about cookies and informed consent in websites and apps. The data produced in the project is encapsulated in public reports. The data collected by the citizen scientists and the project team includes names of websites and apps and audit information about cookies and tracking technologies embedded beneath. Other data collected includes interviews of willing citizen scientists in two CSI-COP newsletters; anonymous surveys a) collected from CSI-COP citizen scientists reflecting on their behaviour post-investigations, and b) views on volunteering and citizen science from the general public. The final piece of data collected in CSI-COP is personal data (names and emails only) of individuals registering to attend CSI-COP's main project dissemination and exploitation event in Brussels in May 2023. The collected data is either made public as a project result, or stored securely where it is maintained in a virtual storage space with limited access for CSI-COP project team. The personal data is set to be destroyed five years after the conclusion of the project.

1: Introduction to CSI-COP Data Management 3

In CSI-COP’s first data management plan (DMP1: D1.8|D7; Shah, Ignat & Pocs, 2020) we detailed how the CSI-COP project would conform to the EU Horizon 2020 open research data pilot. DMP1 presented the initial data collected in the project (research articles) and explained how CSI-COP findings would be made open under the **F.A.I.R.** data management principle: **findable**, **accessible**, **interoperable**, and **reusable**. As a project investigating the compliance of the EU’s general data protection regulation (GDPR) in websites and apps, CSI-COP itself set-up robust procedures to comply with the GDPR. This was achieved in a number of ways beginning with:

1. Setting up a privacy-by-design, no-tracking website with secure header -‘s’ in https: (<https://csi-cop.eu>),
2. Cookie banner on the website stating it “does not use cookies that analyse traffic” (Fig 1).
3. Transparent Privacy Policy: <https://www.csi-cop.eu/privacy-policy/> stating “the website is free of tracking visitors’ movements and navigation around CSI-COP pages” (Box 1).

Figure 1: CSI-COP website: cookie banner at the bottom of the home page

The philosophy of design for the CSI-COP website has been to develop each section (Home, About, etc.) and its sub-pages as privacy-by-default.

The development has involved ensuring the website is free of tracking visitors’ movement and navigation around CSI-COP pages. This means the CSI-COP website does not track from which website a visitor arrived on to a CSI-COP web page, nor does CSI-COP website monitor or record the ‘session’ of each visitor. To this end the CSI-COP website has no visitor tracking on its web pages.

Box 1: Segment of text from CSI-COP website Privacy Policy

This second and follow up data management plan (DMP2; Shah et al., 2022) detailed CSI-COP's data protection impact assessment (DPIA) and how the F.A.I.R principle had been implemented in the project. Additionally, DMP2 presented the manner in which CSI-COP complied with the GDPR, by following the purpose limitation principle in the regulation during the start of citizen science (CS) engagement by only collecting necessary personal data from the general public after providing project participation information and gaining full informed consent (Shah et al., 2022).

This third and last CSI-COP data management plan explains the data produced, and data collected in the final phase of the project from:

- a) CSs and project team investigations of websites and apps;
- b) CSs' anonymous survey to find any change in online behaviour following CS participation in CSI-COP (see Appendix1);
- c) An anonymous survey for the general public regarding their opinion of volunteering and citizen science (see Appendix 2), and
- d) Individuals' name and email following registration to attend the main project dissemination and exploitation event in May 2023 either online or in person.

The next sub-section updates on CSI-COP's F.A.I.R. contribution. Following that, the new produced, the new data collected and collection method, and final data management plan are described.

2: F.A.I.R

CSI-COP continued to follow the F.A.I.R. principle explained in the first and second data management plans (DMP1: Shah, Ignat & Pocs, 2020; DMP2 Shah et al., 2022). Achieving F.A.I.R. was through making CSI-COP results public and openly accessible from the project's website, and from Zenodo open-access platform. The latest results since DMP2 made available for public access are:

1. Interviews of CSI-COP's citizen scientists featured in the project's 9th and 10th newsletters: <https://csi-cop.eu/news-letters/>
2. CSI-COP citizen scientists' investigations in open-access searchable databases in Excel:
 - a. Websites: <https://csi-cop.eu/project-results/citizen-scientists-website-investigations/>
 - b. Apps: <https://csi-cop.eu/project-results/citizen-scientists-app-investigations/>
3. Report on anonymised information about the age, gender, socio-economic and geographical distribution (AGSEG) of CSI-COP's citizen scientists: (Rigler, et al., 2023): <https://csi-cop.eu/project-results/who-are-citizen-scientists/>
4. Taxonomy of Digital Cookies and Online Trackers: <https://csi-cop.eu/project-results/taxonomy-of-cookies-and-online-trackers/>

Results 2), 3) and 4) above are also accessible from **Zenodo** (<https://zenodo.org/>). CSI-COP's public reports are listed in the data map in the Appendix.

3: Allocation of Resources

As explained in DMP1 (Shah, Ignat & Pocs, 2020) the cost to the project for making CSI-COP data F.A.I.R. during the lifetime of the project is part of the project management budget. This has enabled CSI-COP to maintain a living data management plan. The responsibility for data management in CSI-COP lies with all the partners led by Coventry University

In the next section, the new data since the submission of DMP2, after that the new data collection method and secure storage are detailed.

4: New Data

Categories of new data produced and collected between July 2022 and April 2023 are detailed in the next sub-sections, and also tabulated in Appendix 3 (pages 23-26).

4.1: New Data produced

CSI-COP produced project results in various formats, including Excel spreadsheets as searchable databases of citizen scientists' GDPR compliance investigations of websites and apps. The results as new data produced in Period 3 are listed below.

1. Outputs delivered as submissions to the EU and made openly accessible from the website results page and on Zenodo platform:
 - a. Searchable databases of citizen scientists' website (D4.1|D14) and app (D4.2| D16) investigations, and corresponding manuals;
 - b. Public report with anonymised information on CSI-COP citizen scientists' age, gender, socio-economic, and geographic (AGSEG) distribution (D4.3| D17);
 - c. Public report 'Taxonomy of cookies and online trackers' (D5.1|D18).
2. Scientific article '**Challenges and solutions to inclusive citizen science during a pandemic: Perspectives from an EU funded project**'. Submitted for peer-review to journal '*Citizen Science: Theory and Practice*' (one of three scientific publications as part of deliverable D6.2|D21). This will be made open-access on publication.
3. CSI-COP Newsletters available from the project website: <https://csi-cop.eu/news-letters/>
 - a. 7th: August 2022
 - b. 8th: October-November 2022

- c. 9th: December – January 2023
 - d. 10th: March – April 2023
4. Social media posts on Twitter ([@cop_csi](https://twitter.com/cop_csi)) and LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/in/csi-cop-569275227/>).

New data collected is explained in the next sub-section.

4.2: New data collected

The new data collected in period 3 of the project, from June 2022 and April 2023 is listed below:

1. Websites' cookies and trackers audit following citizen scientists' investigations.
2. App permissions and tracking audit following citizen scientists' investigations.
3. Anonymous survey information eliciting change in online behaviour of CSI-COP citizen scientists (see Appendix 1 for blank survey with questions).
4. A general public anonymous survey to find perspectives on volunteering and citizen science (see Appendix 2 for blank survey with questions).
5. Name and email of individuals registering to attend CSI-COP main dissemination and exploitation event in May 2023.

GDPR-compliant collection method of the new data is explained in the next section.

4.2.1: New Data collection method

Period 3 in CSI-COP entailed citizen scientists' participation as data protection and privacy researchers volunteering their own time to investigate websites they visited and apps they used. Figure 2 illustrates the path CSI-COP citizen scientists followed from concerned members of the public to website and app investigators.

Figure 2: Path of CSI-COP citizen scientist investigating websites and apps

4.2.1.1: Website and App investigations

The data collected by CSI-COP citizen scientists and team members, from their data protection and privacy audits of websites and apps as part of work package 4 (WP4), are detailed in the project's publicly available results. Two open access databases (1-website; 2-apps) and corresponding manuals are available from the project website [results page](#), and [Zenodo](#) platform. This data collection is not personal in nature. No CSI-COP citizen scientists' or team members' personal details are included alongside the findings from website and app investigations. The data collected from the investigations are made available and consist purely of non-personal individual data:

1. Website data:
 - a. Name and URL of website;
 - b. Date website investigated;
 - c. Type of website (news, entertainment, etc.);
 - d. Screenshot of website (for validation purposes);
 - e. Brief details on website cookie banner/cookie notice and privacy policy;
 - f. Name of any free website privacy audit tool used to find third-party cookies;
 - g. Details of cookies and other tracking technologies found.
2. App data:
 - a. Name of app;

- b. Type of app (games, health, etc.);
- c. Screenshot of app (for validation purposes);
- d. Details on permissions the app has access to in a device;
- e. If Exodus Privacy tool used to check app for cookies and tracking technologies.

Readers can review CSI-COP CSs website and app investigations by downloading the open-access, searchable databases from the project results page and reading the corresponding manuals. These are available here: <https://csi-cop.eu/projectresults/>

4.2.1.2: CSI-COP Surveys

Two anonymised surveys were prepared in the last period of the project to evaluate CSI-COP project activities and impact (e.g., societal impact). The purpose of gathering the anonymous data from the surveys is to measure the efficacy of the project and deliver analysis for publications, including for peer-review scientific journals. The two surveys prepared are:

- a) CSI-COP citizen scientists: Gain insight into any change in behaviour following participation in the project as website and app GDPR compliance investigators (see Appendix 1);
- b) General public: views on volunteering and citizen science participation (see Appendix 2).

4.2.2 Personal data

Personal data collected in period 3 is for a limited purpose. The personal data collected is the name and email of interested stakeholders registering to attend the project's main dissemination and exploitation event in May 2023.

5: Personal Data Management

To manage the minimal personal data collected in the period covered by this data management plan, CSI-COP's personal data management process is **centralised**. The specific personal data collected is the name and email of individual stakeholders for the explicit purpose of registering for attendance in CSI-COP's **main project dissemination and exploitation event in Brussels in May 2023**. The name and email from an interested stakeholder are collected from an especially created [registration page](#) on the project's website (Figure 3).

Brussels Event Registration:

Register to attend:
 CSI-COP project main event across 23-26 May.
 Come and speak to a citizen scientist about their website and app investigations.
 Try out the, investigate necessity of cookies and trackers found in CSI-COP investigations.
 Please choose your preferred session noting the language(s) the CSI-COP partner offers.

Date of session	DAY	Time: Central European Time (CET)	Language of session	Partner involved
23.05.2023	Tuesday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Finnish	BAR ILAN UNIVERSITY
		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	English and Italian	COVENTRY UNIVERSITY
24.05.2023	Wednesday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Greek and English	PAINEPSTIMIO PETRON (University of Patras)
		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	Hungarian	NOKA TUODOMANYISAN ESZTERLET (NATE)
25.05.2023	Thursday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Spanish	UNIVERSITAT AUTONOMA DE BARCELONA (UAB)
		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	English	IMMER BESSER (IB)
26.05.2023	Friday	MORNING: 10am-12pm	Czech	CEŠKÉ VYSOKÉ UČENÍ TECHNICKÉ V PRAZE (CTU)
		AFTERNOON: 2pm-4pm	Finnish	OULUN YLIOPISTO (UOULU)

Attending online - a Zoom link will be sent

Attendance in person: please note there are limited spaces for attending the event in person, no travel or accommodation costs can be provided for this. Please contact Dr. Huma Shah at ab7778@coventry.ac.uk for further information about in-person attendance

DATE OF SESSION:

CHOOSE SESSION: MORNING: 10AM-12PM AFTERNOON: 2PM-4PM

LANGUAGE OF SESSION:

NAME (REQUIRED):

EMAIL (REQUIRED):

We welcome anyone who uses the Internet to attend our event, including tech and science journalists, web and app developers, data protection professionals, privacy academics, policy-makers as well as members of the public.

Figure 3: CSI-COP Main project dissemination and exploitation event registration page: <https://csi-cop.eu/brussels-event-registration/>

The personal data (name and email), collected via the online registration page (Figure 3) is by CSI-COP Coordinating partner, Coventry University. Coventry University lead the task (T6.3) entailing organising and coordinating partners for the main project dissemination and exploitation hybrid event in May 2023. This collection method is designed for maximum efficacy, and additionally, in order to engage with interested stakeholders with necessary information relating to times of attendance and housekeeping. Collected personal data will be managed centrally by Coventry University and stored in a password-protected Excel spreadsheet maintained securely in CSI-COP's virtual document sharing space: SharePoint. The name and email of a registrant will be passed to the relevant partner only to minimise any data breach. In this way partners can engage with the registrant of their specific-partner session in the main dissemination event. The personal data collected for the main event will be deleted five years after the conclusion of the CSI-COP project in August 2023. While adhering to Article 5(e) GDPR, we will take into account the international data deletion standard [ISO/IEC 27555:2021](#) (Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection — Guidelines on personally identifiable information deletion).

6: Data Security

To keep personal data secure, the names and emails of CSI-COP's citizen scientists are stored separately from their website and app investigations. CSs' names and emails are not accessible to the public and are stored by, and accessibly only to, the relevant project partner in a secure decentralised way, unless a CS has given informed consent for name release after transparent request with purpose. Partners cannot access the names of other partners' citizen scientists, unless a citizen scientist willingly gave an interview for a CSI-COP newsletter ([9th](#) and [10th](#)).

The two open-access, searchable databases realised from work package 4 in the project (website investigations; app investigations) do not present any citizen scientists' personal data. The data accessible in the investigation databases includes information on cookie banners, privacy policies and any cookies or tracking technologies uncovered in websites ([D4.1|D15](#)) and in apps ([D4.2|D16](#)). The taxonomy of cookies and online trackers ([D5.1 | D18](#)) realised from the databases of website and app investigations, will be combined in the production of the final CSI-COP innovation: the **repository of cookies and online trackers** (D5.2| D19). The repository will not contain any personal details of CSI-COP's citizen scientists. This project result is currently under development with all CSs and partner team members' investigations of websites and apps: no CSI-COP citizen scientist or researcher is being associated with any investigation in the repository innovation. The first iteration of the repository will be demonstrated in [CSI-COP's main project event](#) in May. CSI-COP's free and searchable repository of web and app investigations will be made available for the general public from the project website results page at the end of May 2023. The repository will be maintained by the Coordinating partner, Coventry University, after the conclusion of the project in August 2023 for one year. This time-frame is chosen due to the speed of change in the data-protection and online privacy environment, not least due to the emergence of large language models (LLMs) available on the Internet (generative AI), such as ChatGPT, GPT4, BARD, introducing new privacy and data protection concerns.

Before the delivery of CSI-COP's **repository** to the EU at the end of May 2023, the general public will have an opportunity to give their feedback during the main project event across 23-26 May 2023. Feedback gained from the demonstration will be embedded in the final version of this CSI-COP repository tool.

Readers are invited to review CSI-COP project results and join the main event in May 2023 to see the demonstration of the repository :<https://csi-cop.eu/brussels-event-registration/>

7: Ethical Aspects

In addition to investigating GDPR compliance in websites and in apps, CSI-COP has fully complied with the GDPR. Ethical and responsible research and innovation processes set-up in the project were designed to be fully transparent about any data collected. This included the limited purpose of collecting personal data after gaining full informed consent:

- i) To issue certificate on completion of free informal education course 'Your Right to Privacy Online' (see DMP2: Shah et al., 2022);
- ii) To register individuals (e.g. stakeholders) to attend the main project dissemination and exploitation event in May 2023.

CSI-COP gained ethical approval to informally educate under-18s in the project through school visits in the presence of their teachers. The partners gained full informed consent before joining members of the general public in the project as citizen scientists investigating website and apps for GDPR compliance with respect to transparency and informed consent (See DMP2: Shah et al., 2022). In this way, interested members of the public who participated in CSI-COP acquired new knowledge about online data collection methods in websites and apps. Additionally, CSI-COP's citizen scientists gained invaluable practical skills to better manage their personal data while using the Internet (see CSI-COP public report on age, gender, socio-economic and geographical distribution report: Rigler et al., 2023).

This third data management plan has explained the new data produced, and data collected in the final period of CSI-COP. The data storage and deletion plans have also been explained. In this way, CSI-COP has implemented compliance with the EU's data protection regulation, the GDPR, in the project as well as investigated GDPR compliance in websites and apps.

8: References:

CSI-COP Newsletters:

Interview 1 with a citizen scientist in the 9th Newsletter: <https://csi-cop.eu/csi-cops-9th-newsletter/>

Interview 2 with a citizen scientist in the 10th Newsletter: <https://csi-cop.eu/csi-cops-10th-newsletter/>

Rigler, D., Hinsenkamp, M., Shah, H. & Winter, J. (2023). CSI-COP Citizen Scientists Age, Gender, Socio-Economic and Geographical (AGSEG) Distribution Report (4.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7602259>

Shah, H., Ignat, T., & Pocs, M. (2020). *Data Management Plan: Initial*. CSI-COP EU H2020 project report (D1.7/D9 version 1.6). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5705981>

Shah, H., Rigler, D., Hinsenkamp, M., Celentano, U., Ignat, T. & Zhitomirsky-Geffet, M. (2022). *CSI-COP Data Management Plan 2* (4.2.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6785598>

Shah, H. Gialelis, Y., Konstantinopoulos, I., Lantavou, K., Karakonstanti, A., Rigler, D., Stepankova, D., Ignat, A., & Celentano, U. (2023). Taxonomy of Digital Cookies and Online Trackers (7.2.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7801846/>

Zenodo: CSI-COP project open-access reports: <https://zenodo.org/search?page=1&size=20&q=CSI-COP>

Appendix 1: Survey for CSI-COP CS

The anonymous survey for CSI-COP's citizen scientists' only is across pages 14-18 in Appendix 1 and begins below.

Survey for CSI-COP Citizen Scientists

This questionnaire is for members of the public who became CSI-COP citizen scientists by:

1. Completing CSI-COP's free educational course 'Your Right to Privacy Online' (MOOC)
2. Completing the MOOC and the test questions
3. On 2) requested their MOOC completion certificate
4. On 3) completed CSI-COP participant information/informed consent to join the project as Citizen Scientists
5. Completing and submitting website and / or app investigations to their local CSI-COP project partner

This questionnaire seeks to learn if, after joining CSI-COP as citizen scientists, you have changed your online behaviour – please kindly answer the questions overleaf.

1. What browser did you use to access the Internet before you joined CSI-COP as a citizen scientist? For example, Microsoft Edge.
2. **Before joining** CSI-COP as a citizen scientist, did you accept cookies on a website? Please choose from:
 - a. Before joining CSI-COP, I always accepted cookies in websites I visited, because (select all that apply from below)
 - i. Don't know, just accepted
 - ii. Saving time
 - iii. It was convenient
 - iv. I saw no harm in accepting all cookies
 - b. Before joining CSI-COP I checked the cookie notice and /or the website privacy policy for any options about what cookies were and what they were for YES/NO
 - c. Before joining CSI-COP I tried to reject cookies if that option was available on websites I visited. YES/NO
3. Do you use the same browser to access the Internet after joining CSI-COP as a citizen scientist? YES/NO/USE DIFFERENT BROWSERS

4. If you have changed browsers, which browser is your primary one to access the Internet?

Please write your answer in here

5. Do you accept cookies now after investigating websites as a CSI-COP citizen scientist?

Please choose from the below:

- a. I check for options to reject unnecessary cookies, such as third-party cookies for targeting, marketing, personalisation
 - b. I choose the 'Reject All' if that option is available
 - c. I check further for other targeting techniques in websites, for example, 'Legitimate Interest' to object to all targeting
 - d. I still accept all cookies because:
 - i. There is no option to reject cookies on some websites
 - ii. I don't have the time to reject
 - iii. Other, please say
6. Do you use and download apps? YES/NO
7. Did you check permissions in the apps before you joined CSI-COP as a citizen scientist?
YES/NO
8. Do you:

- a. accept default permissions in apps after joining CSI-COP as a citizen scientist?
YES/NO or
 - b. do you now check what permissions an app is requesting and select which permissions you give access to? YES/NO
9. Did you use public wi-fi for example, in cafes, in libraries, on trains, etc., before you joined CSI-COP? YES/NO
10. Do you still use public wi-fi after joining CSI-COP as a citizen scientist? YES/NO
11. Do you use a super-app that controls many functions, such as home surveillance cameras lighting in your house as well as grocery ordering? If so, which super app?
12. This question is for families: do you allow children in your family to have and use smart devices? YES/NO
13. If you so, at what age do you allow the children in your family to have a smart device?
14. If the children in your family use a smart device, do you, or do you ask the children in your family to check:
- a. What apps your child uses on that phone? Please name the type of apps, for example, a messaging app, a games app, a painting app, etc
 - b. What permissions are on the apps on the phone that your child uses? For example, if it is a games app, does the app have permissions to contacts, photos, messages, etc.?
 - c. Does your family use any parental control app to protect children in the family?
YES/NO

15. Would you like to share any other change in your online behaviour as a result of joining CSI-COP as a citizen scientist, or share your views about what you found from your investigations of websites you visited and apps you used?

Please send your completed survey to your local CSI-COP partner.

Appendix 2: Survey for the general public

The anonymous survey for the general public (not CSI-COP citizen scientists) is across pages 19-20 in Appendix 2 and begins below.

QUESTION 1:

Have you ever volunteered, i.e., conducted activities and not been paid as part of your interest in some project seeking volunteer participation?

If yes, please go to Question 2

If no, would you be able to say why?

QUESTION 2

If you have volunteered previously, what kind of project did you participate in and what was your role?

QUESTION 3

If you have volunteered previously, what benefit, if any, did you feel you gained from the volunteering experience?

QUESTION 4

Have you heard of citizen science?

If yes, please go to Question 5

If no, please see this page explaining citizen science: <https://csi-cop.eu/faq/>

QUESTION 5

Have you heard of the CSI-COP citizen science project?

If yes, please go to Question 6

If no, please see this page: <https://csi-cop.eu/about/>

QUESTION 6

If you were willing to volunteer, i.e., do unpaid work in your spare time, what kind of project topic would you be willing to participate in, please choose as many from the list below:

- a. Plastic pollution
- b. Space science
- c. Climate science
- d. Air pollution
- e. Artificial Intelligence and robotics
- f. Online data protection, privacy, and human rights
- g. Other: please say...

{Partners place their contact name and email once translation of this survey2 is completed}

Appendix 3: Data Map

Map of data gathered during Period 3 of CSI-COP project.

Brief description	Data Category	Data type	Metadata	Data format	Type of Persistent identifier	Owner	Data size	To whom outside the project data might be useful?	Publicly available?
Newsletters	Project updates and guest interviews.	Text and images	Photos of events and CSI-COP team members and interviewees.	.PDFs	CSI-COP Newsletter page: News Letters – csi-cop	CSI-COP	7 th – 1.48MB 8 th – 1.78MB 9 th – 2.02MB 10 th – 1.55MB	The general public. Teachers. Citizen science projects. EU Commission. Data Protection Officers. Privacy professionals. Policy makers.	Yes
Project deliverable D4.1 D15 Database	Websites investigated by citizen scientists	Names and URL of websites	Image of website, information on cookies, tracking tech, and name of free website audit tool used.	Excel spreadsheet	CSI-COP website project results page: Citizen Scientists' Website Investigations – csi-cop	CSI-COP	503Kb	EU Commission. Web developers. Data Protection Officers. Privacy professionals. Policy makers. Higher education course directors. Tech and Science Journalists. Citizen science researchers. Human rights advocates.	Yes
Project deliverable report accompanying	Document version 1	Text	Authors, keywords, file type, file size,	PDF	DOI from Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.7472957	CSI-COP	4.1MB	EU Commission. Web developers. Data Protection Officers. Privacy professionals. Policy makers. Higher education course directors. Tech and	Yes

to D4.1 D15 database			embedded images					Science Journalists. Citizen science researchers. Human rights advocates.	
Project deliverable D4.2 D16	Apps investigation by citizen scientists	Names of Apps	Image of app, names of App permissions to functions in a device, tracking tech, and name of free App audit tool	Excel Spreadsheet	CSI-COP website project results page: Citizen Scientists' App Investigations - csi-cop	CSI-COP	126Kb	EU Commission. App developers. Data Protection Officers. Privacy professionals. Policy makers. Higher education course directors. Tech and Science Journalists. Citizen science researchers. Human rights advocates.	Yes
Project deliverable report accompanying database to D4.2 D16	Document version 1	Text	Authors, keywords, file type, file size, embedded images	PDF	DOI from Zenodo: 10.5281/zenodo.7472879	CSI-COP	646.8Kb	EU Commission. App developers. Data Protection Officers. Privacy professionals. Policy makers. Higher education course directors. Tech and Science Journalists. Citizen science researchers. Human rights advocates.	Yes
Scientific article	Document for peer-review	Text	Authors, keywords, file type, file size, embedded images	.PDF	DOI once paper accepted for publication	CSI-COP	378Kb	EU Commission. Pandemic Researchers. Citizen science researchers.	Will be open-access following peer-review process completion
Project deliverable D4.3 D17 CSI-COP Citizen	Document: Version 4.2	Text	Authors, keywords, file type, file size,	PDF	DOI from: 10.5281/zenodo.7602259	CSI-COP	16.9MB	Citizen science researchers. EU Commission.	Yes

Scientists Age, Gender, Socio- economic and Geographic (AGSEG) Distribution report			embedded images						
Project deliverable D5.1 D18 Taxonomy of Cookies and Online Trackers	Document: version 7.2.1	Text	Authors, keywords, file type, file size, embedded images	PDF	DOI from Zenodo: 10.5281/zenod o.7801846	CSI-COP	34MB	Privacy researchers, data protection policy makers; web and app developers, tech journalists, data management planners	Yes
Survey2	Document	Text	Text questions	WORD	N/A	CSI-COP	3.28MB	Citizen science researchers. Data protection and online privacy researchers. Policymakers.	Yes, for the survey questions
Survey 3	Document	Text	Text questions	WORD	N/A	CSI-COP	3.28MB	Data protection and privacy professionals. Policymakers.	Yes, for the survey questions
Name of general public member registering to attend CSI- COP main event in Brussels	Row in a password protected, confidential Excel sheet.	Text	Name and surname	Excel sheets	N/A	General public member	Not applicable	Not applicable as this data will not be made available outside of the CSI-COP project consortia unless the citizen scientist gives informed consent to be interviewed and be made known to a journalist or other stakeholder.	On request by external parties with transparent reason and purpose provided, and if informed consent received from registrants.

Email of general public member/ learner completing CSI-COP course	Row in a confidential password protected Excel sheet.	Text and numbers	Email address	Excel sheets	N/A	General public member	Not applicable	Not applicable as this data will not be made available outside of the CSI-COP project consortia unless the citizen scientist gives informed consent to be interviewed and be made known to a journalist or other stakeholder.	On request by external parties with transparent reason and purpose provided, and if informed consent received from registrants.
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